

Trolling the trolls – fighting dark participation with digital vigilantism

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Abstract

In this paper, we explore how digital vigilantism has been employed as a strategy to mitigate destructive behaviors known as dark participation. We argue that communities can be empowered to effectively defend online spaces against *enshittification* by turning the tactics of trolls and haters against themselves and beating them in their own game, a form of online jiu jitsu, if you will.

In January 2025, Meta declared its intention to eliminate fact-checking and content filtering on its primary social media platforms, Instagram and Facebook, to “reaffirm [its] fundamental commitment to free expression” (Meta 2025). Following Elon Musk's acquisition of Twitter in 2022, his initial action was to dismiss the teams responsible for content moderation and reinstate accounts that had previously been banned for disseminating racist, transphobic, or violence-glorifying content, as well as conspiracy theories, all under the guise of “protecting freedom of speech.” The outcome in both instances was a significant rise in hate speech and disinformation, accompanied by a deterioration of online discourse, a phenomenon that Cory Doctorow (2023) termed *enshittification*. This social dynamic, characterized by a blend of despair and rage interspersed with irony and sarcasm, serves as an ideal environment for swarms of trolls, haters, and shit-posters engaged in all forms of dark participation.

Dark participation (Lutz and Hoffmann 2017) seeks to undermine constructive discourse and progressively convert online spaces into toxic and hostile environments, particularly affecting marginalized and vulnerable populations. It has also become a tactic in *culture wars* (Rao 2018) for digital spaces and is systematically employed by alt-right and reactionary movements to silence people and create hostile spaces for political opponents (e.g. “woke” leftists, climate activists, feminists), stigmatized and marginalized groups (“girls, gays, and theys”), and racial and ethnic minorities. This includes orchestrated shitstorms initiated by influential actors and accounts that pursue their victims across various platforms, often those with little to no moderation, such as Twitch, Reddit, or Telegram. The tactic involves the stirring up a sense of persecution, an “us” vs “them” dynamic and the subsequent mobilization of swarms of trolls and haters emboldened by the safety of anonymity. What tactics can effectively counter this development and empower communities within these quasi-public *third spaces*?

Strategies to counter dark participation have focused mainly on two approaches: (1) *platform governance*, that is, moderation, reporting community guideline violations (e.g., hate speech, disinformation), or flagging or removing harmful content or accounts. (2) *Individual defense mechanisms*: options to report offensive or criminal behavior to platforms or the police (e.g., harassment, insult, incitement to hatred). These strategies can be effective as long as online platforms commit to sanction destructive user behavior (and put sufficient resources into their enforcement), and as long as users can rely on law enforcement to effectively prosecute

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criminal offenses committed online. However, more often than not, both strategies failed. A more performative and collaborative approach examined in this research is the strategy of (3) *counter-swarmling*, a practice that is helping empowering communities to combat dark participation.

Communities have started to use swarming as a novel method of political advocacy. Online swarms are networks of interconnected individuals, content, and bots, enabling members to act autonomously while achieving a collective effect through a common focus that is reinforced by the algorithmic feedback loops of their online environments (Fernández, 2023). Generation Z, especially, leverages social media to highlight contemporary political issues and spark conversations around them. Notably, TikTok has become a key platform for young people to voice their political opinions and participate in political advocacy (Serdar 2020). In June 2020, a swarm of K-Pop fans and Teens organized on TikTok to troll the Trump election campaign by buying up thousands of tickets for a rally held in Tulsa, Oklahoma only then not to show up leaving the venue largely empty (Lorenz et al. 2020). Swarm culture is reflected in memes, internet challenges or streaming hits, but it can also transgress into offline spaces as happened in fluid and impulsive political movements like #BLM or #MeToo.

In this paper, we demonstrate how counter-swarms can act as a form of cyber-vigilantism against dark participation and social injustices are using strategies of weaponizing visibility (Trottier 2017). Numerous instances on social media have demonstrated that individuals engaged in dark participation tend to withdraw from debates when they lose the shield of anonymity and face accountability for their offenses—ideally in front of a vast audience. While this form of activism, employing counter-swarmling tactics, may appear radical, it serves as a means of self-defense. In an increasingly toxic atmosphere surrounding online discussions and attacks against individuals by swarms of trolls, it has allowed victims and vulnerable communities to push back effectively.

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